

1 **A validated method for the characterization and quantification of extractable and**
2 **non-extractable ellagitannins after acid hydrolysis in pomegranate fruits, juices, and**
3 **extracts.**

4

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24 **ABSTRACT**

25 Pomegranates are one of the main highly valuable sources of ellagitannins. Despite
26 the potential health benefits of these compounds, reliable data on their content in
27 pomegranates and derived extracts and food products is lacking, as it is usually
28 underestimated due to their complexity, diversity, and lack of commercially available
29 standards. This study describes a new method for the analysis of the extractable and non-
30 extractable ellagitannins based on the quantification of the acid hydrolysis products that
31 include ellagic acid, gallic acid, sanguisorbic acid dilactone, valoneic acid dilactone, and
32 gallagic acid dilactone, in pomegranate samples. The study also shows the occurrence of
33 ellagitannin *C*-glycosides in pomegranates. The method was optimized using a
34 pomegranate peel extract. To quantify non-extractable ellagitannins, freeze dried
35 pomegranate fruit samples were directly hydrolysed with 4 M HCl in water at 90 °C for
36 24 h followed by extraction of the pellet with dimethyl sulfoxide/methanol (50/50, v/v).
37 The method was validated and reproducibility was assessed by means of inter-laboratory
38 trial, showing high reproducibility across six laboratories with relative standard
39 deviations below 15%. Their applicability was demonstrated in several pomegranate
40 extracts, different parts of pomegranate fruit (husk, peels and mesocarp) and commercial
41 juices. A large variability has been found in the ellagitannin content (150-750 mg of
42 hydrolysis products/g) and type (gallagic acid/ellagic acid ratios between 4 and 0.15) of
43 the 11 pomegranate extracts studied.

44

45 **Keywords:** Ellagitannin / Acid hydrolysis / Ellagic acid / Pomegranate / Inter-laboratory
46 reproducibility

47 **INTRODUCTION**

48 Polyphenols, mainly consisting of ellagitannins (ETs), are the predominant class of
49 phytochemicals of pomegranate fruits.^{1,2} ETs are also found in other fruits and nuts
50 (strawberries, raspberries, blackberries, cloudberries, muscadine grapes, almonds and
51 walnuts among others) characterized as hydrolyzable conjugates containing one or more
52 hexahydroxydiphenyl (HHDP) groups that esterify a sugar, usually glucose.^{3,4} Among
53 the ETs occurring naturally in pomegranate, the unique gallagylesters, punicalagin, and
54 punicalin are the predominant ones.^{5,6} They mainly occur in the husk (pericarp) and peels
55 (mesocarp) and are extracted out into the juice upon commercial processing of the whole
56 fruits.^{2,5} Most of the health promoting potential of pomegranate has been attributed to
57 these polyphenolic compounds.⁷⁻⁹ Punicalagin, and ETs in general, show antioxidant,
58 anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and anticarcinogenic activities.^{10,11} However the
59 bioavailability of ETs is very low and in the human gastrointestinal tract, they release
60 ellagic acid, which is further metabolized by the colonic microbiota to urolithins.¹² Some
61 biological effects of urolithins have started to be reported.¹³ The fate of other ellagitannin
62 components in the gut (gallagic acid, valoneic acid, sanguisorbic acid, and C-glycosidic
63 ellagitannins) and their interaction with gut microbiota remains unknown.

64

65 Considering the interest in ETs due to their potential health properties, their correct
66 characterization and quantification is of relevance. The quantification of the total ellagic
67 acid released from ETs that could be accessible to the gut microbiota to produce urolithins
68 and other metabolites would provide valuable information to understand the health effects
69 of ellagitannin-containing fruits. Correct identification and quantification of ETs is
70 difficult due to their structural complexity (strong tendency to form dimeric and
71 oligomeric derivatives), their diversity and the lack of commercially available reference

72 standards of sufficient purity.¹⁴ In the early stages of ETs research, colorimetric methods
73 (sodium nitrite, rhodamine and potassium iodate assays), mainly based on the reaction of
74 gallic acid or ellagic acid with different reagents, were widely used.¹⁵ Although these
75 methods are simple and fast, they generally do not provide accurate quantitative data.
76 Different High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) methods have been
77 reported in the literature for the determination of phenolic compounds in pomegranate
78 samples and related products.^{14,16-18} However, most of them refer to compounds extracted
79 in aqueous and hydroalcoholic extracts (extractable polyphenols), but ellagitannins can
80 also remain un-extracted in the extraction residue, as they can be partly soluble or
81 insoluble in the extraction solvent or remain covalently bound to cell walls and other
82 macromolecules of the fruit.^{19,20}

83 In some fruits, ETs were previously quantified as total ellagic acid based on the fact
84 that, when these compounds are exposed to acids or bases release hexahydroxydiphenic
85 (HHDP) acid which undergoes spontaneous lactonization to ellagic acid. Many authors
86 have reported the total ellagic acid content after acid hydrolysis, mainly in berries and
87 nuts.²¹⁻²⁴ Most of the existing procedures rely solely on the quantification of released
88 ellagic acid and only some of them²⁵ consider other compounds formed during hydrolysis
89 which may provide helpful information on the chemical structure of the naturally
90 occurring ETs. Despite the numerous methods for acid hydrolysis described in the
91 literature, an optimized and validated method for the determination of total ellagic acid
92 and other reaction products in pomegranates after hydrolysis is still lacking.

93 The objectives of this study were: 1) to optimize a method for a more complete
94 characterization of pomegranate ETs by quantitating the ellagic acid and other reaction
95 products released after acid hydrolysis, 2) to carry out an inter-laboratory trial to examine

96 the reproducibility of the method, and 3) to demonstrate the applicability of this method
97 in pomegranate extracts, and different parts of pomegranate fruits and juices.

98

99 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

100 **Chemicals and samples.** Standards of ellagic acid, punicalagin ($\geq 98\%$ HPLC purity)
101 and gallic acid were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). Vescalagin was
102 kindly supplied by Prof. Stéphane Quideau, Université de Bordeaux, France. Methanol
103 (MeOH) and acetonitrile were purchased from J. T. Baker (Deventer, The Netherlands)
104 and dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) from Labscan (Dublin, Ireland). Formic acid 98% and
105 HCl 37% were obtained from Panreac (Barcelona, Spain). Ultrapure water from a Milli-
106 Q system (Millipore Corp., Bedford, MA) was used throughout this experiment. All
107 chemicals and reagents were of analytical grade.

108

109 Eleven pomegranate extracts were supplied by Laboratorios Admira (Alcantarilla,
110 Murcia, Spain). Pomegranate juice was provided by a juice processor (AMC, Murcia,
111 Spain). Pomegranates of the cultivar 'Mollar' (Elche, Spain) were purchased in a
112 supermarket. The fruits were manually separated into husk (pericarp), peels
113 (membranes/mesocarp) and arils (containing the seeds) and then were freeze dried and
114 grounded with a mixer grinder. The powders and extracts were kept in a desiccator prior
115 to analyses.

116

117 Stock solutions of punicalagin (1 mM), vescalagin (0.5 mM) and gallic acid (10 mM)
118 were prepared in MeOH and ellagic acid (3 mM) was dissolved in DMSO. Calibration
119 curves were prepared by appropriate dilutions of the stock solutions in methanol at ten

120 different concentration levels from 1 to 500 μM for punicalagin and vescalagin and from
121 1 to 1000 μM for ellagic acid and gallic acid

122

123 **Polyphenol extraction from pomegranate samples.** The homogenized powder of
124 pomegranate samples (extracts and freeze-dried pomegranate fruit parts) were weighted
125 (75 mg) and dissolved with 5 mL of a mixture of MeOH/DMSO/H₂O (40/40/20, v/v/v)
126 containing 0.1% HCl. Samples were vortexed for 10 min and centrifuged at 3500 g
127 (Eppendorf 5804R) for 10 min. The supernatant was filtered through a 0.45 μm
128 polyvinylidene difluoride (PVDF) filter (Millipore) and measured with HPLC-ESI-UV-
129 MS/MS.

130

131 **Acid hydrolysis optimization of pomegranate samples.** Optimal acid hydrolysis of ETs
132 was completed using the following protocol: Accurately weighed freeze-dried samples
133 (50 mg) were placed in 10 mL pyrex screw-cap tubes, and 3.34 mL of water and 1.66 mL
134 of 37 % HCl (final concentration of 4 M) were added. Samples were vortexed for 1 min
135 and incubated in an oven at 90 °C for 24 h. After incubation, the samples were let to cool
136 to room temperature and pH was adjusted to 2.5 with 10 M and 5 M of NaOH. The tubes
137 were centrifuged for 10 min at 3500 g (Eppendorf 5804R). The supernatant was recovered
138 and the volume was adjusted to 10 mL with ultrapure water. The supernatant was filtered
139 through a 0.45 μm PVDF filter before injection onto the HPLC column. The resulting
140 pellets, containing the majority of water insoluble compounds, were dissolved into 10 mL
141 DMSO:MeOH (50/50, v/v) by vortexing for 2 min and after centrifugation as above the
142 supernatants were filtered through a 0.45 μm PVDF filter. When the concentration in
143 pellet was high, as in the case of pomegranate extracts, the samples were diluted 1:10

144 with DMSO:MeOH (50:50 v/v) before injection onto the HPLC column. Hydrolysis
145 experiments were carried out in triplicate.

146

147 For juice samples, 3.34 mL of juice was mixed with 1.66 mL of 37% HCl (final
148 concentration 4 M HCl), vortexed for 1 min and incubated in an oven at 90 °C for 24 h.
149 The hydrolysis and analysis was performed as described above for solid samples.

150

151 **HPLC-ESI-UV/MS/MS (IT) analysis.** The analyses of hydrolyzed and non-hydrolyzed
152 samples were carried out on an Agilent 1100 HPLC system equipped with a photodiode
153 array detector and an ion-trap mass spectrometer detector (Agilent Technologies,
154 Waldbronn, Germany). Chromatographic separation was performed on a reverse phase
155 Pursuit XRs C18 column (250 mm × 4 mm, 5 μm particle size) (Agilent Technologies,
156 Waldbronn, Germany). The mobile phases were water with 1% formic acid (A) and
157 acetonitrile (B) following a gradient profile: 0–20 min, 5–30% B; 20–30 min, 30–55%
158 B; 30–38 min, 55–90% B; 38–40 min, 90% B; and then returned to the initial conditions.
159 A volume of 10 μL of sample was injected onto the column operating at room temperature
160 and a flow rate of 1 mL/min. Scan wavelength was performed in DAD at 200–600 nm
161 with scan rate of 2.5 Hz (2 second response) and scan step of 2 nm. UV chromatograms
162 were recorded at 280 and 360 nm with bandwidth of 8 nm. The ion trap (IT) mass
163 spectrometer was equipped with an electrospray interface (ESI). Nitrogen was used as
164 drying gas with a flow of 11 L/min at a temperature of 350 °C and nebulizing gas at
165 pressure of 65 psi. The capillary voltage was set at 4 kV. Mass scan (MS) and daughter
166 (MS/MS) spectra were recorded in negative mode in the range of m/z 100–1500 with
167 target mass of 500. Maximum accumulation time of ion trap and the number of MS

168 repetitions to obtain the MS average spectra were set at 200 ms and 3, respectively.

169 Compound stability was set at 75%

170

171 Peak identification was performed by comparison with authentic reference standards and

172 when they were not available by using the diode array spectral characteristics, molecular

173 mass, and fragmentation pattern of the compounds. Ellagic acid (360 nm), punicalagin

174 (360nm), vescalagin (280nm) and gallic acid (280nm) were used as external standards to

175 quantify compounds in non-hydrolyzed samples. In the hydrolysed samples calibration

176 curve of ellagic acid at 360 nm was used to quantify all the hydrolysis products, except

177 for gallic acid that was quantified with its own standard at 280 nm.

178

179 **Hydrolysis method validation.** The limits of detection (LODs) were determined based
180 on a signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) of 3 and of 10 for the limit of quantification (LOQ).

181 Due to the lack of available standards for most of the hydrolysis products, except for

182 ellagic acid, and the absence of pomegranate matrices free of these compounds,

183 recoveries for each compound after the hydrolysis protocol were calculated as follows:

184 $\text{Recovery \%} = (\text{quantity of compound obtained after the optimized protocol} / \text{total quantity}$

185 $\text{of compound after adding two more extraction of the pellet with DMSO}) \times 100$. After the

186 optimized protocol (hydrolysis in water and extraction of the pellet with DMSO:MeOH

187 (50/50, v/v)) the resulting pellet was extracted two more times with pure DMSO to ensure

188 the complete extraction of all hydrolysis products. DMSO has been reported to be

189 adequate for the solubilisation of ellagic acid, highly insoluble in water and other

190 solvents.²⁶ The quantity recovered applying the optimized protocol was expressed as

191 percentage of the total amount calculated in the sample.

192

193 The effectiveness of the optimized protocol and the effect of acid hydrolysis on pure
194 ellagic acid were checked by hydrolysis of known amounts of punicalagin (225 μM) and
195 ellagic acid (200 μM), respectively. The optimized protocol (hydrolysis in water and
196 extraction of the pellet with DMSO:MeOH (50/50, v/v)) was applied to both standards.

197

198 Precision was evaluated by determining repeatability (intra-day), intermediate precision
199 (inter-day and different instruments/analysts) and reproducibility (inter-laboratory).

200 Repeatability was evaluated by analyzing data from three measurements of the same
201 hydrolyzed sample three times in the same day. For the intermediate precision the same
202 sample was analysed in three different days and the method was also applied by ten
203 different analysts in the same laboratory using the same instrumentation (HPLC DAD
204 equipment as above) and by the same analyst on different equipment (Agilent 1100,
205 Agilent 1200 Infinity Series, Agilent 1220 Infinity Series and Hitachi Elite LaChrom
206 HPLC). Besides, a large inter-laboratory reproducibility study was conducted analysing
207 the same pomegranate extract by six European laboratories using different instruments
208 and chromatographic columns (see below).

209

210

211 **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

212

213 **Identification of ellagitannins in pomegranate extracts.** In order to choose the most
214 appropriate extract to be used in the optimization of the hydrolysis protocol (i.e. the one
215 with the highest/most diverse hydrolysable tannin content), different pomegranate
216 extracts were analyzed by HPLC-DAD-ESI-MS/MS. The HPLC-UV chromatograms at
217 280 and 360 nm of the pomegranate peel extract selected for the hydrolysis optimization

218 trial are shown in **Figure 1**. Twenty three hydrolyzable tannins and ellagic acid
219 conjugates were tentatively identified by their retention time, molecular mass, fragments
220 obtained by MS/MS experiments, and their UV spectra (**Table 1**). These compounds had
221 been previously described ^{2,17,18} and include free ellagic acid, ellagic acid glycosides,
222 gallagyl esters, and more complex ETs comprising combinations of hexahydroxydiphenic
223 acid, gallic acid, and glucose. Due to the large number of ETs and isomers, complex
224 chromatograms with many unresolved peaks were obtained, especially at 280 nm (**Figure**
225 **1B**). The complexity of the chromatograms, together with the absence of commercial
226 standards, hampers the correct identification and quantification of pomegranate
227 ellagitannins. Therefore, acid hydrolysis of the samples and quantification of the reaction
228 products could be a good alternative method for ET characterization and quantification.

229

230 **Acid hydrolysis optimization.** Several methodologies for the acid hydrolysis of ETs,
231 especially from berries and nuts, have previously been reported.²²⁻²⁴ In most of these
232 methods, a primary extraction of the polyphenols with hydro-organic mixtures, usually
233 acetone/water or MeOH/water was applied. After evaporation the extracts were usually
234 dissolved in MeOH (methanolysis) or in MeOH/water prior to hydrolysis.²² This
235 extraction process, however, does not allow the quantification of non-extractable
236 ellagitannins, leading to an underestimation of these polyphenols. Studies by Vrhovsek
237 et al.²⁵ and Da Silva Pinto et al.²¹ concluded that acetone/water was the best solvent for
238 the initial extraction and 2N trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) for 1 h at 120 °C in water and 4 M
239 HCl for 6 h at 90 °C in MeOH the best hydrolysis conditions for the determination of total
240 ellagic acid in strawberries and raspberries, respectively. As a first step in the optimization
241 process these two hydrolytic conditions were tested in the selected pomegranate extract
242 both in MeOH and water. The freeze dried samples were hydrolyzed after an initial

243 extraction with acetone/water (0.6 g of pomegranate sample with 25 mL of acetone/water)
244 and also a direct hydrolysis was tested. **Figure 2** shows the reaction compounds produced
245 during the hydrolysis of pomegranate samples and the ETs from which they have been
246 formed (described in detail in the next section). The content of the main compounds
247 detected after the different hydrolysis conditions, original ETs (punicalagin and two
248 isomers of punicalin) and reaction products (gallic acid, gallagic acid dilactone, ellagic
249 acid, sanguisorbic acid dilactone, and valoneic acid dilactone) is shown in **Table 2**.
250 Although similar results were obtained for most of the compounds with and without
251 previous extraction, direct hydrolysis was chosen as the preferred approach as it required
252 less time and solvents and allowed quantification of both the extractable and non-
253 extractable compounds. In general, larger amounts of reaction products were obtained
254 after 6 h of hydrolysis with 4 M HCl at 90 °C. The reaction was better carried out in water
255 as the hydrolysis in MeOH generated methylated derivatives (methyl gallate, methyl
256 valoneic acid dilactone, and methyl punicalin, among others), preventing the correct
257 quantification due to the lack of authentic standards.^{22,24} Although there was a drawback
258 of using water, namely the very low solubility of ellagic acid in aqueous media²⁷ which
259 caused some of the hydrolysis products to remain precipitated in the pellet, re-extraction
260 of the pellet with DMSO / MeOH (50:50, v/v) proved to be very efficient at dissolving
261 highly insoluble compounds such as ellagic acid, gallagic acid dilactone, and valoneic
262 acid dilactone and these were subsequently recovered completely from the pellet (**Table**
263 **2**).

264

265 Hydrolysis of freeze dried samples with 4 M HCl at 90 °C in water and subsequent
266 extraction of the pellet with DMSO/MeOH (50:50, v/v) was finally selected as the best
267 conditions for maximum hydrolysis and recovery. However, 6 hours were not sufficient

268 to complete the hydrolysis as punicalin and other ETs were still present (**Table 2**). To
269 find the most efficient hydrolysis of pomegranate ETs, different hydrolysis times (0, 1, 2,
270 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, and 24 h) were tested. **Figure 3** shows the evolution of punicalagin and
271 the main reaction products after the hydrolysis of the pomegranate extract (three
272 replicates).

273

274 The kinetics showed the fast hydrolysis of punicalagin that disappeared after 2 h of
275 incubation and the much slower hydrolysis of the punicalin produced, taking 24 h to reach
276 a complete hydrolysis. Two punicalin isomers were detected; punicalin 2 was already
277 present in the original extract while punicalin 1 was only detected after acid hydrolysis.
278 The punicalins were hydrolyzed at different rates, punicalin 2 being hydrolyzed faster
279 than punicalin 1. Both punicalins increased gradually during acid hydrolysis as a product
280 of the release of ellagic acid from punicalagin, and then decreased when gallagic acid
281 dilactone was released (**Figure 3**). This shows that the release of ellagic acid from
282 punicalagin by acid hydrolysis is much more favored than the hydrolysis of the gallagyl
283 ester to release gallagic acid dilactone, as it needs up to 24 h to be completed. Ellagic acid
284 reached a maximum after 4 h because of the fast hydrolysis of punicalagin and this value
285 was maintained up to 24 h. Longer periods of treatment with HCl did not release more
286 ellagic acid. Gallagic acid dilactone, originating from punicalagin and punicalin,
287 increased over time reaching the maximum concentration after 24 h, as well as gallic acid
288 and valoneic acid dilactone. Sanguisorbic acid dilactone reached steady-state
289 concentration between 6 and 10 h.

290

291 Finally, hydrolysis for 24 h with 4 M HCl at 90 °C in water and subsequent extraction of
292 the pellet with DMSO/MeOH (50/50, v/v) was selected as the most suitable pretreatment

293 to yield maximum recovery for the main hydrolysis products of pomegranate ETs (see
294 graph of total hydrolysis products in Figure 3).

295

296 **Reaction products obtained after the hydrolysis.** Several reaction products were
297 detected after acid hydrolysis of pomegranate extracts. **Figure 4A** shows the HPLC-UV
298 chromatograms of the supernatant (360 and 280 nm) and pellet (360 nm) of a
299 pomegranate extract after acid hydrolysis. All these compounds were identified by their
300 retention time, molecular mass, fragmentation pattern, and the spectral properties shown
301 in **Table 3**. The UV spectrum for each compound (**Figure 4B**) is also useful for the
302 identification of the hydrolysis products when only HPLC with UV diode array detectors
303 are available for analysis. All compounds (except gallic acid) exhibit two major
304 absorption maxima. The first one was around 256 nm and the second one in the region of
305 350-400 nm with slight differences in the UV maxima depending on the compound. As
306 indicated before, the main reaction products identified and quantified were ellagic acid,
307 gallagic acid dilactone, gallic acid, and two compounds with m/z 469 consistent with
308 ellagic acid derivatives in which an additional gallic acid is linked to the ellagic acid
309 molecule through an ether bond (**Figure 5**). Traces of punicalin (less than 1%) were also
310 observed and indicated that the hydrolysis of this compound was incomplete. In general,
311 the main hydrolysis products were ellagic acid and gallagic acid dilactone. In particular,
312 the detection of gallagic acid dilactone could be considered as an unequivocal signal of
313 the presence of pomegranate, as it was produced by hydrolysis of the unique and
314 characteristic ETs (gallagyl esters) of pomegranate, punicalagin and punicalin. After acid
315 hydrolysis, one molecule of punicalagin releases one molecule of ellagic acid and one of
316 gallagic acid dilactone. This last compound could also be released from punicalin
317 (**Figure 2**). The detection of gallic acid was indicative of the presence of gallotannins and

318 other gallic acid-containing products. The two compounds with m/z 469 showed different
319 fragmentation patterns and UV spectra (**Table 3**, **Figure 4**, **Figure 5**). In both cases, the
320 presence of an M-44 fragment (m/z 425) was observed, this being consistent with the loss
321 of CO₂ as could be expected for phenolic with a free carboxylic group. According to
322 literature these isomers could correspond to valoneic acid dilactone and sanguisorbic acid
323 dilactone. The only difference is that the hydroxyl that links the hexahydroxydiphenoyl
324 group (HHDP) to the galloyl group belongs to the HHDP group or the galloyl group
325 (**Figure 2**). According to the literature^{¡Error! Marcador no definido.} the hydrolysis of strawberry
326 ellagitannins produces sanguisorbic acid dilactone in addition to ellagic acid. So, in order
327 to identify both isomers the optimized hydrolysis protocol was applied to a strawberry
328 sample. One peak with m/z 469 was detected at 13.46 min, the same retention time of the
329 compound **4** that was tentatively identified as sanguisorbic acid dilactone. The presence
330 of both isomers after hydrolysis indicates the occurrence in pomegranate extracts of other
331 complex ETs with linkages in their structure involving an additional galloyl group linked
332 to the HHDP ester group.

333

334 Apart from the major compounds, other minor analytes with UV-VIS absorbance spectra
335 similar to that of ellagic acid were detected after the hydrolysis. Two of them with m/z
336 631 and 463 exhibited fragmentation profiles characteristic of C-glycosidic compounds
337 with the typical losses of 60, 90, 120, and 150 m.u., often accompanied by an additional
338 loss of water ($-m/z$ 18 m.u.). Several isomers for each compound were detected in the
339 MS-MS analysis (**Figure 5**). Different isomers of ellagic acid C-glucoside (**8**) were
340 identified. These could be produced after the hydrolysis of C-glycosidic ellagitannins.
341 The occurrence of different isomers indicates that the original HHDP-C-glucoside can be
342 cycled in different conformations after the hydrolysis. The presence of these reaction

343 products suggests that C-glycosidic ETs such as casuariin, punicalagin, punicalagin,
344 vescalagin/castalagin etc. could be present in the extract. The identification of compounds
345 **9-10** was not possible with the instrumentation used in this experiment, although
346 information about fragmentation patterns and UV spectra is provided in **Table 3**. Ellagic
347 acid C-glucosides represented less than 3% of the total hydrolysis products, indicating
348 that in general, C-glycosidic ellagitannins were minor constituent of pomegranate
349 samples.

350

351 **Method validation.** For the quantitation of non-hydrolyzed samples limits of detection
352 (LOD) and quantification (LOQ), considering the whole protocol, were estimated at 0.06
353 mg/g and 0.20 mg/g for vescalagin, 0.07 mg/g and 0.24 mg/g for punicalagin and 0.01
354 mg/g and 0.03 mg/g for both ellagic acid and gallic acid. For the quantitation of
355 hydrolyzed samples LOD and LOQ, considering the whole protocol, were 0.03 mg/g and
356 0.10 mg/g for both ellagic acid and gallic acid.

357 The effectiveness of the optimized hydrolysis protocol was checked by hydrolysis of a
358 known amount of punicalagin standard (225 μ M). Complete hydrolysis of punicalagin
359 was observed after 24 h with the presence of two main peaks: ellagic acid and gallagic
360 acid dilactone (**Figure 6**). Other minor compounds were observed (representing less than
361 5%) probably due to the presence of trace amounts of other ETs in the punicalagin
362 standard (standard purity \geq 98% HPLC isolated from pomegranate). Hydrolysis of
363 punicalagin would theoretically yield 1 mol of ellagic acid and 1 mol of gallagic acid
364 dilactone per mol of punicalagin. UV response factors were similar for both compounds,
365 indicating that the ellagic acid calibration curve can be used as a good proxy for the
366 accurate quantitation of gallagic acid dilactone as no standard was available of the latter
367 compound.

368

369 Recoveries of hydrolysis products in pomegranate extracts after hydrolysis were between
370 97 and 99% and no decomposition of ellagic acid was observed up to 24 h.

371

372 Method precision was evaluated by determining repeatability, intermediate precision and
373 reproducibility. The optimized method has a high precision with relative standard
374 deviation (RSD) of peak areas below 5.6% for intraday precision and below 7.5% for
375 interday precision. Assessment of the intermediate precision by means of using different
376 instruments or having various analysts prepare the samples was estimated at 9.5% and
377 14%, respectively. Finally, reproducibility of the method was assessed by means of an
378 inter-laboratory study conducted by six European laboratories. Reproducibility of the
379 method for most of the main compounds was below 15% (**Table 4**). Only valoneic acid
380 dilactone showed higher values (33%) probably due to its low intensity as this compound
381 is usually present in low concentrations (around 2% of the total hydrolysis products).

382

383 **Comparison with the conventional quantitation (without hydrolysis).** The
384 quantitative results obtained with the new hydrolysis method were compared with those
385 produced with a conventional method (**Table 5**). The conventional method for
386 pomegranate ETs quantitation involves the individual assessment of each compound after
387 a hydro-organic extraction of the samples. Due to the lack of available standards each
388 compound was quantified with the most appropriate calibration curve (indicated in **Table**
389 **5**). Direct quantification of extractable ellagitannins using HPLC-DAD and external
390 standards (punicalagin, vescalagin, ellagic acid, gallic acid) yielded 549.1 mg/g d.w.
391 extract (**Table 5A**). When the corresponding equivalents of ellagic acid, gallagic acid
392 dilactone and gallic acid, were calculated, the total amount of the equivalents that should

393 be released after hydrolysis of the extractable ellagitannins reached 349.3 mg/g and this
394 value should be compared with that obtained after direct hydrolysis without
395 hydroalcoholic extraction that amounted 635.8 mg/g d.w (**Table 5B**). The results show
396 that around 300 mg/g of the hydrolysis products were corresponding to non-extractable
397 ellagitannins (either non-extracted or not quantifiable with the direct HPLC-DAD
398 analysis). Other minor compounds (those with valoneic acid bilactone, sanguisorbic acid
399 bilactone, and *C*-glycosyl ellagitannins) were not quantified in the conventional analysis
400 without hydrolysis (**Table 5A**), as their quantification in the chromatograms of the non-
401 hydrolyzed extracts was not possible. After hydrolysis a small amount of these
402 compounds was detected (90.5 mg/g of the valoneic and sanguisorbic acid dilactones and
403 18 mg/g of ellagic acid *C*-glucoside), therefore increasing even more the content of ETs
404 in the analyzed extract (750.6 mg/g; dw) (**Table 5B**).

405

406 As indicated before, the presence of a high background and unresolved peaks in the
407 chromatograms (especially at 280 nm, see **Figure 2**) together with the absence of
408 available standards for most of the compounds, could lead to an underestimation when
409 using the conventional method. The hydrolysis method has shown to be a good alternative
410 for quantitation purposes.

411

412 **Application of the method to different pomegranate samples.** The optimized method
413 was successfully applied to different pomegranate extracts finding large differences in
414 the ellagitannin content (**Figure 7**). Pomegranate peel extracts have recently attracted
415 interest because of their potential use as natural food preservatives and nutraceuticals.^{28,29}
416 Industrial scale extraction of phenolic compounds from pomegranate peel is carried out
417 by using solvents such as water and ethanol, or their mixtures. The content of hydrolysis

418 products ranged from 150 mg /g extract up to 750 mg/g showing that different plant
419 materials and different extraction and purification processes had been applied for extract
420 preparation. In addition highly significant chemical differences ($p < 0.01$) in the
421 ellagitannin composition were observed.

422 The high variability observed among the different pomegranate extracts was especially
423 important in the amount and ratio of ellagic acid and gallagic acid dilactone, indicating
424 large differences in the presence of the gallagyl esters punicalagin and punicalin. One
425 pomegranate extract containing mainly punicalagin should have a gallagic acid
426 dilactone/ellagic acid ratio around 2. Ratios above 2 indicate that the extract is richer in
427 punicalin, and ratios below 2 indicate that the extracts are richer in ellagitannins based on
428 ellagic acid or extracts with larger amounts of free ellagic acid. Thus extracts 2, 3, and 10
429 (**Figure 7**) show gallagic acid dilactone/ellagic acid ratios that indicate that punicalagin
430 was the main ellagitannin, while extracts 5 and 6 contain mainly punicalin and extracts 4
431 and 11 contain mainly ellagic acid based ellagitannins. Furthermore, the presence or
432 absence of other hydrolysis products is indicative of other ETs content. This variability
433 is in agreement with the literature where the use of different solvents for peel phenolic
434 extraction is reported to yield different phenolic content ratios and associated different
435 antioxidant activity.²⁸ Previous studies for the analysis of extractable ETs in pomegranate
436 extracts using HPLC had reported ETs contents of 330 mg/g d.w.³⁰ and 220 mg/g d.w.³¹,
437 values which are smaller than those found in the present study, particularly after
438 hydrolysis that takes into account the non-extractable ETs.

439

440 The applicability of the method was also tested on different parts of a pomegranate fruit:
441 husk (pericarp), peels and membranes (mesocarp), arils and commercial juices.
442 Quantitative results are shown in **Table 6**. The highest concentration of ellagic acid and

443 other hydrolysis products occurred in the husk followed by the peels and only traces were
444 present in the arils. This is in agreement with previous reports in which individual
445 quantitation of ETs with conventional extraction methods were assayed.^{2,5}

446

447 Further research will be conducted in order to apply this methodology to other
448 ellagitannin-rich food products including berries and nuts, and to extrapolate the present
449 findings to a simplified method that can be easily used for the routine analysis of
450 pomegranate ETs in all laboratories and industry.

451

452

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458 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

459 **Figure 1.** HPLC-UV chromatograms at 360 nm (A) and 280 nm (B) of the non-
460 hydrolyzed pomegranate peel extract. This sample was chosen for the hydrolysis
461 optimization. Numbers refer to compounds described in **Table 1**.

462

463 **Figure 2.** Structures of the hydrolysis products (in green) of pomegranate samples and
464 the original ETs (in red) from which may have been formed.

465

466 **Figure 3.** Evolution of punicalagin and reaction products after direct hydrolysis of
467 pomegranate peel extract with 4 M HCl at 90 °C in water and subsequent extraction of
468 the pellet with MeOH/DMSO (50/50, v/v). Total hydrolysis products refer to the sum of
469 gallic acid, valoneic acid dilactone, sanguisorbic acid dilactone, gallagic acid dilactone
470 and ellagic acid. Results are expressed as mean±SD (n=3).

471

472 **Figure 4.** A) HPLC-UV chromatograms of the supernatant (360 and 280 nm) and pellet
473 (360 nm) of a pomegranate peel extract after 24 hours of hydrolysis. B) UV spectrum of
474 the reaction products detected after the hydrolysis of pomegranate samples. Numbers
475 refer to compounds described in **Table 3**.

476

477 **Figure 5.** HPLC-DAD-MS-MS analysis of the supernatant obtained after acid hydrolysis
478 of the pomegranate extract. UV chromatogram at 352 nm. Extracted ion chromatograms
479 (EIC) at m/z 631, m/z 463 and m/z 469. Numbers refer to the compound described in
480 **Table 3**.

481

482 **Figure 6.** HPLC-UV chromatogram at 360 nm of the mixture of supernatant and pellet
483 obtained after the hydrolysis of punicalagin standard. Numbers refer to the compound
484 described in **Table 3**.

485

486 **Figure 7.** Content of the main hydrolysis products in different pomegranate extracts,
487 expressed as mg of compound/g DW.

Table 1. Characterization of the main tannins present in the pomegranate extract selected for hydrolysis optimization.

N°	Compound	Retention time (min)	[M-H] ⁻	Fragments	λ _{max}
1	HHDP-hexoside	2.33-3.35	481	463, 421, 301, 275, 191	238
2	Galloyl-HHDP-glucuronide	4.45/6.15	649	605, 497, 361, 301	238, 270
3	Galloyl-HHDP-hexoside	4.58/5.76/7.79/8.85/9.30/10.97/12.78	633	615, 463, 301, 275, 229*	236, 270
4	Digalloyl-hexoside	4.88/6.45	483	331, 313, 169	270
5	Gallagyl derivative	5.11	1101	1083, 1057, 781, 601	n.d.
6	Gallagyl-hexoside (punicalin)	5.48	781	721, 601, 299	262, 378
7	Bis-HHDP-hexoside (pedunculagin I)	5.99/6.84/7.63/8.95/9.30/11.26/12.48	783	765, 481, 301, 275*	242, 262sh
8	Ellagitannin 1	6.46/8.21/9.30	707	1113, 783, 633, 613, 481, 301	260, 378
9	Galloyl-gallagyl-hexoside (pedunculagin III)	6.62/6.97	933	915, 781, 721, 601	260, 378
10	Vescalagin/castalagin	8.15	933	631, 451, 301	n.d.
11	Punicalagin	8.42/10.02	1083	781, 721, 601, 299	268, 378
12	Digalloyl-gallagyl-hexoside	9.09/10.65	1085	933, 783, 631, 601, 451	258, 378
13	Ellagitanin 2	10.97	799	781, 479, 301	242, 268
14	Galloyl-bisHHDP-hexoside (casuarin)	11.36	935	783, 633, 301	242, 278sh
15	Digalloyl HHDP-glucuronide (punigluconin)	11.46	801	781, 649, 499, 347, 301	242, 278sh
16	Digalloyl-HHDP-hexoside (pedunculagin II)	12.09/14.18/15.93	785	685, 633, 483, 301*	262
17	Ellagic acid hexoside	13.95	463	301	254, 365
18	Galloyl-HHDP-DHHDP-hexoside (granatin B)	15.05	951	933, 613, 631, 301	367, 378
19	Galloyl-ellagic acid hexoside	16.35	615	463, 301	265, 365
20	Ellagic acid pentoside	16.56	433	301	255, 360
21	Ellagic acid-deoxyhexoside	17.00	447	299	255, 364
22	Ellagic acid	17.79	301	229, 185	255, 370
23	Dimethyl EA hexoside	18.17	491	328, 313, 298	250, 370

*Not all the fragments are present in the isomers detected at different times; n.d.: below the limit of detection; sh: shoulder.

(DHHDP): dehydro-hexahydroxydiphenic acid; (HHDP): hexahydroxydiphenic acid.

Compounds with the same numbers are represented in Figure 1.

Table 2. Total content (mg of compound/g DW) of the original ellagitannins and hydrolysis products obtained under different hydrolysis conditions during the protocol optimization (N=3).

	Punicalin 1^{a*}	Punicalina 2^{a*}	Punicalagin^a	Gallic acid^{b*}	Valoneic acid dilactone 1^{c*}	Sanguisorbic acid dilactone^{c*}	Gallagic acid dilactone^c	Ellagic acid^c
Previous extraction with acetone/water								
2 M TFA 120 °C 1 h in MeOH	1.4*	32.3*	178.5	11.3*	0*	5.1*	0	14.4
2 M TFA 120 °C 1 h in water	13.8	126.4	17.3	35.3	9.1	14.5	0	19.8
4 M HCl 90 °C 6 h in MeOH	13.6*	37.1*	0	11.9*	3.4*	6.2*	0	13.9
4 M HCl 90 °C 6 h in water	39.6	22.8	0	44.9	4.0	7.2	0	41.0
Direct hydrolysis								
2 M TFA 120 °C 1 h in MeOH	1.4*	31.3*	217.6	13.1*	0*	5.1*	0	11.1
2 M TFA 120 °C 1 h in water	15.5	126.5	17.7	36.6	12.3	15.6	0	16.2
4 M HCl 90 °C 6 h in MeOH	14.2*	48.7*	0	13.8*	5.8*	8.8*	0	12.6
4 M HCl 90 °C 6 h in water	38.3	24.7	0	23.6	8.1	20.0	0	49.4
Pellet re-extracted with MeOH/DMSO								
4 M HCl 90 °C 6 h (water) + pellet (total amount)	38.3+0 (38.3)	24.7+0 (24.7)	0+0 0	23.6+1.3 (24.9)	8.1+2.2 (10.3)	20.0+50.0 (70.0)	0+189.1 (189.1)	49.4+190.6 (239.9)
4 M HCl 90 °C 24 h (water) + pellet (total amount)	6.4+0 (6.4)	0+0 0	0+0 0	34.5+2.4 (36.9)	10.1+4.2 (14.3)	15.1+61.0 (76.1)	0+338.0 (338.0)	45.4+215.4 (260.8)

*Methylated derivatives of these compounds were not quantified and appeared in the chromatograms of the samples hydrolysed in MeOH

^aQuantified at 360 nm with punicalagin ^bQuantified at 280 nm with gallic acid. ^cQuantified at 360 nm with ellagic acid

Table 3. Compounds identified in HPLC-UV-MS after 24 h hydrolysis of pomegranate extracts.

	Main compounds	Retention time (min)	[M-H]⁻	MS/MS*	λ_{max}
1	Punicalin	3.00	781	721, 601 , 299	258, 380
2	Gallic acid	4.77	169	125	272
3	Valoneic acid dilactone	8.22	469	425 → 407 , 397, 300, 271	256, 308sh, 374
4	Sanguisorbic acid dilactone	13.32	469	425 → 301 , 299, 271	256, 308sh, 366
5	Gallagic acid dilactone	14.45	601	-	256, 308sh, 380
6	Ellagic acid	17.35	301	271 , 229	256, 310sh, 372
Minor compounds					
7	Valoneic acid dilactone C-glucoside	7.701	631	571, 541, 511, 469, 451 , 425	n.d.
8	Ellagic acid C-glucoside	12.39/ 13.98 /15.28/ 15.75/16.14	463	445 , 403, 373 , 343 , 313, 300	256, 310sh, 372
9	Unknown 2	19.09	427	409,367, 355 , 337, 325, 300	258, 332sh,360sh, 374
10	Unknown 3	19.94	451	433, 407, 379, 338	260, 378, 400sh
11	Unknown 4	20.61	425	301, 299 , 285, 271	256, 308sh, 368

*In bold the main fragments in MS².

Compounds with the same numbers are represented in Figure 4.

Table 4. Inter-laboratory study for the determination of the hydrolysis products of ellagitannins in pomegranate extracts after acid hydrolysis. Final concentration of the hydrolysis products are expressed as the mean \pm SD of three replicates in mg of compound/g DW.

Laboratory	LC Instrument	Column	Valoneic acid dilactone	Sanguisorbic acid dilactone	Gallagic acid dilactone	Ellagic acid	Total
CEBAS	Agilent 1100 HPLC, DAD	Agilent Pursuit XRs C18 (250 x 4mm, 5 μ m)	14.3 \pm 1.4	76.2 \pm 5.1	338.0 \pm 23.9	260.9 \pm 37.7	689.3 \pm 24.3
VITO	Waters Acquity UPLC PDA	Alltima C18 (250 x 4.6 mm, 5 μ m)	11.7 \pm 0.4	80.3 \pm 1.5	250.4 \pm 11.8	245.1 \pm 8.4	587.5 \pm 21.5
NOFIMA	Agilent 1100 HPLC, DAD	Betasil C18 (250 x 2.1 mm, 5 μ m)	12.3 \pm 2.1	84.7 \pm 6.7	285.4 \pm 18.1	240.3 \pm 10.5	622.7 \pm 36.9
TUBITAK	Shimadzu SPD-M20A Prominence HPLC PDA	Zivak C18 (250 x 4.6 mm, 5 μ m)	7.9 \pm 0.6	72.1 \pm 0.9	283.5 \pm 11.9	230.4 \pm 6.3	593.9 \pm 18.5
HELSINKI	Waters Acquity UPLC, PDA	Acquity UPLC HSS T3 C18 (150 x 2.1mm, 1.8 μ m)	7.1 \pm 2.4	53.0 \pm 5.7	259.2 \pm 33.9	209.9 \pm 15.4	529.2 \pm 59.4
IFR	Agilent 1100 HPLC, DAD	Luna C18 (250 x 4.6 mm, 5 μ m)	17.5 \pm 1.8	73.8 \pm 0.4	300.0 \pm 6.3	292.1 \pm 8.6	683.4 \pm 12.8
Average			11.8	73.3	286.1	246.4	631.3
SD			3.9	110	31.3	28.0	59.2
RSD (%)			33.1	14.9	10.9	11.4	9.4

Hydrolysis products were quantified with calibration curve of ellagic acid at 360 nm.

Table 5. Compounds quantified in the pomegranate peel extract (extract 1 in **Figure 7**) used during the optimization. **A)** Without hydrolysis (expressed as mg/g DW) and the calculated equivalents of ellagic, gallagic and gallic acids as mg /g DW present in the quantified compounds. **B)** After acid hydrolysis (expressed as mg/g DW).

<u>A) Without hydrolysis</u> <u>(extractable compounds)</u>		Quantified	Calculated equivalents mg/g DW		
Nº	Compound	mg/g DW	Ellagic acid	Gallagic acid dilactone	Gallic acid
1	HHDP-hexoside ^a	2.4	1.5	-	-
3	Galloyl-HHDP-hexoside ^a	13.8	6.6	-	3.7
4	Digalloyl-hexoside ^b	17.4	-	-	12.2
6	Punicalin ^c	8.3	-	6.4	-
7	Bis-HHDP-hexoside ^a	67.3	51.9	-	-
8	Ellagitannin 1 ^c	14.9	-	-	-
9	Galloyl-gallagyl-hexoside ^c	2.7	-	1.7	0.5
11	Punicalagin ^c	192.7	53.7	107.0	-
12	Digalloyl-gallagyl-hexoside ^c	7.2	-	3.6	2.0
13	Ellagitannin 2 ^a	86.4	-	-	-
15	Digalloyl-HHDP-glucu ^b	35.4	13.3	-	15.0
16	Digalloyl- HHDP-hexoside ^a	11.4	4.4	-	4.9
17	Ellagic acid-hexoside ^d	18.8	12.2	-	-
18	Galloyl-HHDP-DHHDP-hexoside ^a	38.3	12.2	-	6.8
19	Galloyl-ellagic acid-hexoside ^d	0.8	0.4	-	0.2
20	Ellagic acid- pentoside ^d	0.8	0.5	-	-
21	Ellagic acid-deoxyhexoside ^d	5.7	3.8	-	-
22	Ellagic acid ^d	24.9	24.9	-	-
	Total	549.1	185.3	118.7	45.3
<u>B) After acid hydrolysis</u> <u>(extractable + non-extractable)</u>					
	Compounds	mg/g DW			
	Punicalin ^d	6.4			
	Gallic acid ^b	36.9			
	Gallagic acid dilactone ^d	338.0			
	Ellagic acid ^d	260.9			
	Total	635.8 (640.7 considering punicalin)			
	Valoneic acid dilactone ^d	14.3			
	Sanguisorbic acid dilactone ^d	76.2			
	Ellagic acid C-glucoside ^d	18.0			
	Grand Total	750.6			

^a Quantified at 280 nm with vescalagin. ^b Quantified at 280 nm with gallic acid.

^c Quantified at 360 nm with punicalagin. ^d Quantified at 360 nm with ellagic acid.

Table 6. Quantification of hydrolysis products in different parts of pomegranate fruit (mg/g DW) and in pomegranate juice (mg/L). Results are expressed as the mean \pm SD of three replicates.

	Extract	Husk (pericarp)	Peels Mesocarp	Arils	Juice
Punicalin	6.4 \pm 0.1	0.7 \pm 0.1	0.5 \pm 0.1	-	-
Gallic acid	36.9 \pm 1.3	3.3 \pm 0.6	2.1 \pm 0.1	-	-
Valoneic acid dilactone	14.3 \pm 1.4	1.3 \pm 0.5	1.4 \pm 0.1	-	11.0 \pm 1.6
Sanguisorbic acid dilactone	76.2 \pm 5.1	11.8 \pm 0.4	10.7 \pm 0.2	0.3 \pm 0.0	109.4 \pm 2.0
Gallagic acid dilactone	338.0 \pm 23.9	86.6 \pm 1.4	73.8 \pm 1.2	0.5 \pm 0.1	438.9 \pm 12.4
Ellagic acid	260.9 \pm 37.7	62.6 \pm 0.2	38.7 \pm 2.1	0.7 \pm 0.1	811.1 \pm 24.5
Total	732.6 \pm 23.2	166.0 \pm 3.6	126.6 \pm 3.1	1.5 \pm 0.2	1370.4 \pm 40.1

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

Figure 5.

Figure 6.

Figure 7.

